

Results

Effect of Acidity : The maximum colour intensity was obtained in the range of 4 to 7M hydrochloric acid medium.

Effect of Reagent : The absorbance increased rapidly as the mole-ratio of reagent to vanadium increased from 1 : 1 to 6 : 1. Above this ratio (up to 100 : 1) the absorbance was practically the same.

The colour system was found stable for 24 hours and the order of mixing of reagent was not critical.

Beer's Law : Beer's law is obeyed from concentration range of 1.50 to 5.50 ppm.

Effect of Foreign Ions : The ions listed below do not interfere even when the weight ratio of each to vanadium was 200 : 1.

Li(I), K(I), Cu(II), Ag(I), Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), U(VI), Pb(II), Cd(II), As(III), Ti(IV), borate, oxalate, fluoride and ammonium. However, Zr(IV), Ce(IV), Mo(VI), and W(VI) interfere.

Titanium(IV) interferes with PBHA but it does not interfere with N-o-chlorophenylcinnamohydroxamic acid.

Determination of Vanadium in Steel : Vanadium was determined in B.C.S. steel. The steel solutions were prepared by the reported method¹⁶⁻¹⁷. The results of the analysis are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN B.C.S. STEEL

B.C.S. Steel No.	Vanadium found %	Certified value %V
64a alloy steel	1.545	1.57
241/1 high speed steel	1.540	1.57
252 alloy steel	0.450	0.46

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. G. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing facilities. One of them (Miss S. K. A.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of a fellowship.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR, "N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1972.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and B. K. PAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 43.
3. S. P. BHARGAVA and N. C. SOGANI, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1971, **255**, 36.
4. D. C. BHURA and S. G. TANDON, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **53**, 379.

5. P. MURUGAIYAN, "Complexes of Cerium with Substituted Benzohydroxamic Acids", M.Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1966.
6. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **66**, 39.
7. H. L. KAPOOR, Y. K. AGRAWAL and P. C. VERMA, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 193.
8. B. K. PAL, B. K. MITRA and S. CHATTOPADHYAYA, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 554.
9. ABBASI, A. SHAHID, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **48**, 714.
10. U. TANDON and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 583.
11. S. G. TANDON and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 583.
12. U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12**, 143.
13. V. K. GUPTA and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 753.
14. A. K. MAJUMDAR and GAYATRI DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 147.
15. P. W. WREST, *J. Chem. Edu.*, 1941, **18**, 528.
16. F. D. SNELL and G. T. SNELL, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc. New York, 1949, Vol. II, Chapter 24.
17. S. G. CLARKE, *Analyst*, 1927, **52**, 466.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Microgram Amounts of Nickel(II) with Thiosalicylidene Ethylenediimine*

A. R. SAPLE and D. N. PATKAR

Chemistry Department, University of Bombay, Bombay-400098

Manuscript received 27 June 1978, revised 20 October 1978; accepted 22 December 1978

In the present paper, the reaction of thiosalen with nickel(II) has been utilised to develop a new sensitive method for determination of traces of nickel.

Thiosalen reacts with Ni(II) in weakly acidic medium to form a purple red complex which is soluble in aqueous acetone medium containing $\geq 60\%$ acetone. This reaction enables detection of up to 0.2 μg of Ni by the spot test technique.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm cells. An Elico Li-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements. Thiosalen was prepared by the method of Beck¹. The chloroform solution of the reagent obtained was standardised by titration with a standard lead tetracetate solution in acetic acid medium using quinizarin indicator according to the method recommended by Verma and Bose² for mercaptans. A concentrated ($\sim 10^{-3} M$) solution of the reagent was used

* Paper presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Bangalore, December 12-15, 1976.

for analytical work to keep CHCl_3 content of solutions to a minimum ($\leq 5\%$ v/v).

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectra: Spectral curve of the reagent at pH 3.0 shows two maxima at 330 nm and 400-410 nm respectively. The curve for the Ni(II) complex at pH 3.0 against reagent blank exhibits two peaks at 380 nm ($\epsilon = 3350$) and 505 nm ($\epsilon = 2760$) respectively. The latter wavelength has been chosen for analytical work and appropriate reagent blanks were used for absorption measurements on the complex as the reagent has some absorption at this wavelength.

Effect of pH: Spectral curves of the Ni(II) complex at different pH in the acidic medium are very similar in the pH region 2.0-4.1, in which the same complex species is presumably formed. The absorbance at 505 nm is maximum and constant in the pH region 2.0-3.5.

Stability of the Colour: Development of the full colour intensity of the complex is complete within 20 min and the absorbance is not significantly changed up to at least 4 hr. Absorbance is constant in the temperature range 10-45°.

Procedure for the Determination of Nickel: To a suitable aliquot (≤ 2 ml) of an acidic sample solution containing 5-100 μg of nickel, add 0.5 ml of thio-salen solution in CHCl_3 , followed by sufficient acetone and make up to 10.0 ml, adjusting the pH to 3.0 ± 0.5 , and keeping the acetone content at 75% (v/v). Mix and keep for 20 min. Measure the absorbance at 505 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same way but without Ni(II) solution.

Beer's Law, Sensitivity, Precision and Accuracy: The purple coloured Ni(II) complex adheres to Beer's law in the range 0.5-10.0 μg of Ni(II)/ml. The molar absorptivity is 2.76×10^4 at 505 nm and the Sandell sensitivity of the method is 0.02 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The precision and accuracy of the method tested by analysing samples containing 4.0 μg of Ni(II)/ml, gave the average of ten determinations as 4.00 ± 0.05 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The variance and the standard deviation were found to be 0.0005 and 0.022 respectively.

Interference Studies: CN^- , SCN^- , S^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, citrate, tartrate and EDTA interfere. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ti^{4+} and Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , do not interfere. V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} are tolerated upto 15 ppm each for 4.0 ppm of Ni(II). Pd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} interfere strongly.

References

1. G. BECK, *Mikrochemie*, 1948, 33, 188.
2. K. K. VERMA and S. K. BOSE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 65, 236.

Estimation of Allyl Alcohol, Crotyl Alcohol and Cinnamyl Alcohol with Chloramine-B

H. S. YATHIRAJAN, RANGASWAMY

and

D. S. MAHADEVAPPA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry,
Manasa Gangotri, Mysore-570006

Manuscript received 15 June 1978,
revised 25 October 1978; accepted 18 January 1979

CONJUGATED alcohols such as allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl alcohol have a number of important applications. Allyl alcohol finds a number of industrial applications in the preparation of resins, plasticisers, pharmaceuticals and many organic compounds. Crotyl alcohol finds use as a lachrymator, herbicide and soil fumigant, while cinnamyl alcohol is employed as a flavouring agent and in perfumery. Chloramine-B (CAB) has received considerable attention as a new oxidimetric reagent,¹⁻² and was first proposed by Afanas'ev.³ CAB is a stable compound with slightly higher active chlorine content⁴ than its analogue chloramine-T. During an investigation of the oxidation of alcohols by CAB, it was found that allyl, crotyl and cinnamyl alcohols undergo oxidation with a two electron change and substantial amounts of the alcohol can be estimated by a proper adjustment of reaction conditions. The present communication reports an elegant method for the estimation of allyl and crotyl alcohol in aqueous solution and cinnamyl alcohol in glacial acetic acid and ethanol-water (50 : 50 v/v) media, using CAB. Back titration procedures have been developed as the reaction was not instantaneous.

Experimental

Materials and Methods:

Allyl alcohol (Merck, corrected b.p. 97.1°, $n_D = 1.412$) and crotyl alcohol (Fluka, b.p. 125°, $n_D = 1.424$) were used without further purification. Cinnamyl alcohol (Naarden, corrected b.p. 256.6°) was distilled under reduced pressure. The purity of the compounds was checked by phthalation with phthalic anhydride in pyridine.⁵ The required quantity of (allyl and crotyl) alcohol was accurately weighed and dissolved in the proper solvent, while glacial acetic acid or ethanol-water (50 : 50 v/v) was used as solvents for cinnamyl alcohol. Chloramine-B was prepared⁶ by passing pure chlorine through benzene sulphonamide dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (4M) over a period of 1 hour at 70°. The mass obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from water. The purity of the compound was checked by estimating the amount of active chlorine present in the compound.⁷ An aqueous solution of CAB was prepared and standardised by the iodometric method. All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity. Standard buffer